

INTRADERMAL IMMUNE RESPONSES IN CATTLE VACCINATED WITH RECOMBINANT Bm95 AND LOCAL *Boophilus microplus* WHOLE EXTRACT ANTIGEN

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Abstract

Eighteen healthy cross bred cattle of about 2 years age having no previous exposure to ticks were selected from Instructional Bovine Farm, RVC, Kanke, Ranchi (Jharkhand). Engorged adult *Boophilus microplus* female ticks were reared for hatching, larval emergence, Local *B. microplus* larval whole extract antigen (BmWE_{Ag}) preparation and tick challenge infestation. Bm95 recombinant tick antigen was obtained from Indian Immunological Ltd., Hyderabad and BmWE_{Ag} was prepared in laboratory. Experimental cattle were divided into three groups (A, B and C) of six animals in each. Group A and B were inoculated with 1 ml of Bm95 (200µg protein/ml) and 1 ml of BmWE_{Ag} (250µg protein/ml) respectively intramuscular on zero day and second dose in the same amount on 15th day after primary dose whereas group C kept as an unvaccinated control. All animals were challenged with 100 unfed larvae of *B. microplus* reared in laboratory on day 30, day 70 and 120 day post immunization (DPI). Intradermal Immune Response as skin sensitivity test was recorded highly positive on day 60 and day 40 day post vaccination (DPI) in Bm95 group and BmWE_{Ag} group vaccinated animals.

Key words: Bm95 recombinant antigen, *Boophilus microplus* antigen, Skin Sensitivity Test, Tick larval, Tick challenge and intradermal immune response.

Introduction

The cattle ticks *Rhipicephalus microplus* (Formally called *Boophilus microplus*) are the most common blood-sucking ectoparasites that spread serious haemoprotozoan diseases among cattle and buffaloes (Cafrun *et al.*, 1995). Tick infestation causes significant economic losses in entire world especially in tropical and sub-tropical countries in the terms of decrease yield of milk and meat product etc. This can be controlled by reducing tick population which is not so easy. There are many conventional ways to control ticks in which chemical method is more appreciable among all these (Martins *et al.*, 2002). A major landmark has been achieved in the development of two commercially available vaccines (in Australia and in Cuba) using highly immunogenic Bm86 protein (molecular weight 89 kDa) present in the tick gut membrane and plays a role in endocytosis. Keeping these in mind, the present investigation was planned to assess the intraderma immune responses in cattle inoculated with both the immunogens, Bm95 and BmWE_{Ag} by measuring skin sensitivity test response against *B. microplus* infestation in cattle.

Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out on eighteen healthy cross bred cattle calves of about 2 years age and having no previous exposure to ticks. They were selected and segregated from Instructional Bovine Farm, RVC, Kanke, Ranchi. Engorged adult female ticks (*Boophilus microplus*) were collected from naturally infested cattle herds in and around Ranchi. They were washed and placed in B.O.D. incubator at temperature 28 ± 1°C and relative humidity (R.H.) 85 ± 5 %. After oviposition, larval emergence were used for the preparation of antigens and challenged on experimental animals.

Bm95 recombinant vaccine: Bm95 recombinant tick antigen was obtained from Indian Immunological Ltd., Hyderabad. As per the details provided by the supplier, the source of the antigen was *B. microplus*. Briefly, Bm95 (*Boophilus microplus*), which is a concealed tick gut antigen and final protein concentration in the formulated vaccine was 200µg/ml.

Local *B. microplus* larval whole extract antigen (BmWE_{Ag}): The larval antigen was prepared as per the standard method (Vanden *et al.*, 2003) with minor modification. The protein concentration (Lowry *et al.*, 1951) of supernatant antigen was 250µg/ml.

Experimental cattle were divided into three groups (A, B and C) of six animals in each. Group A and B were inoculated with the first dose of 1 ml of Bm95 (200µg protein/ml) and 1 ml of BmWE_{Ag} (250µg protein/ml) respectively intramuscular on zero day and the second dose in the same amount of respective antigens on day 15 after primary immunization whereas group C were kept as controls. For the assessment of intradermal immune responses of both the antigens, all animals were challenged with 100 unfed larvae of *B. microplus*

reared in laboratory on day 30, day 70 and 120 DPI. These larvae were released on both the ears (50+50) of each cattle and ears were covered and tied with cloth ear bags. All the vaccinated and unvaccinated cattle were subjected to skin sensitivity test *in-vivo* before and after immunization at monthly interval up to 6 months. The skin of neck region was the site of injection and an area of 2 x 2 inches in the middle of the neck region was shaved and cleaned with ethanol. The thickness of the skin was measured (mm) before injection of antigen with the help of slide calipers then the animals were injected intradermally (I/D) 0.1 ml of Bm95 and BmWE_{Ag} antigen in group A and group B, respectively with a sterilized hypodermic 1ml syringe with 22 gauge needle forming a clear bead. The same quantity of each antigen (Bm95 and BmWE_{Ag}) was also inoculated in unvaccinated control animals intradermally at two different sites. Thickness of the skin was measured after 0.5, 1, 6, 24, 48 and 72 hours. At the time of maximum delayed hypersensitivity reaction (48 hours), the skin biopsy was taken for histopathological examination.

The histopathological examination of the skin biopsied tissues was carried out as per the method of Culling (1974) in the Department of Veterinary Pathology, RVC, Kanke, Ranchi. A small portion of each tissue was cut and fixed in 10 percent routine fixative formalin and then washed over night in running tap water. After preparing paraffin blocks, the tissues were cut in to section of 0.5 to 1.0 µm sizes with the help of a microtome. Further, the cut sections were stained by routine haematoxylin and eosin stain and mounted for examination under microscope. Test of significance among the groups using two-way analysis ANOVA (Snedecor and Cochran) was done and by using Win STAT (2003) software system.

Results and Discussion

The results of skin sensitivity test in animals immunized with Bm95 and BmWE_{Ag} antigens along with their un-immunized control counterparts have been shown in Table no. 1. In both the vaccinated groups there was evidence of redness and inflammatory swelling at the antigen inoculated sites up to 48 hours which reduced thereafter up to 72 hours. A typical skin thickness was observed in Bm95 on 60th day (8.27±0.20) and BmWE_{Ag} vaccinated group on 30th day (7.27±0.19) post vaccination, after that it was found to be significantly (P<0.01) decreased to 7.22±0.08 in Bm95 and 4.07±0.09 in BmWE_{Ag} on 180th day. The control animals showed almost no change in skin thickness during different tick challenge infestations. Similar findings have also been reported by Riek (1956); Wikel *et al.* (1978); Bechara and Szabo (1984); Binta and Cunningham (1984); Girardin and Brossard (1985) and Das (1988). In the present study, antigen-specific delayed type of hypersensitivity skin reactions was observed in animals immunized with Bm95 and BmWE_{Ag} immunogens.

Table no. 1: Status of skin sensitivity test (Intradermal) in calves on different days before and after vaccination and challenge

Groups (No. of animals)		A (6)	B (6)	C (6)
Nature of vaccine		Bm95	BmWE _{Ag}	Unvaccinated
Before vaccination	0 DAY	2.38±0.05 ^a	2.35±0.04 ^a	2.37±0.05 ^a
Post vaccination	30 th day	^B 7.67±0.16 ^{bc}	^B 7.27±0.19 ^c	^A 2.40±0.06 ^a
First challenge on 35 th day	60 th day	^C 8.27±0.20 ^d	^B 7.00±0.08 ^c	^A 2.35±0.08 ^a
Second challenge on 70 th day	90 th day	^C 8.17±0.18 ^d	^B 6.95±0.14 ^c	^A 2.28±0.09 ^a
Third challenge on 120 th day	120 th day	^C 7.98±0.24 ^{cd}	^B 6.62±0.09 ^d	^A 2.62±0.06 ^b
	150 th day	^C 8.00±0.17 ^{cd}	^B 5.35±0.08 ^c	^A 2.65±0.06 ^b
	180 th day	^C 7.22±0.08 ^b	^B 4.07±0.09 ^b	^A 2.38±0.06 ^a

Values having the same superscripts in column (small) and row (capital) did not differ significantly

Fig. no. 1: Showing typical delayed (48 hours) skin hypersensitivity reaction in calf Immunized with Bm95 antigen.

Fig. no. 2: Showing typical delayed (48 hours) skin hypersensitivity reaction in calf immunized with BmWE_{Ag} antigen.

Histopathological examination of the skin biopsies taken at the time of maximal reaction showed moderate accumulation of edematous fluid in the deeper dermal layers and excessive infiltration of mononuclear cells specially lymphocytes and macrophages in case of Bm95 vaccinated animals (Fig. no. 3) whereas edematous changes was milder with infiltration of few mononuclear cells in case of BmWE_{Ag} vaccinated animals (Fig. no. 4). This swelling became more indurated and indicated delayed cutaneous hypersensitivity reaction. This type of skin reaction was absent in non-sensitized control group of the animals.

Fig. no. 3: Showing excessive infiltration of lymphocytes and macrophages in dermal layer of skin in Bm95 vaccinated animal.

Fig. no. 4: Showing excessive infiltration of lymphocytes and macrophages in dermal layer of skin in BmWE_{Ag} vaccinated animal.

Histopathological examination of the skin biopsies taken at the time of maximal reaction showed moderate accumulation of edematous fluid in the deeper dermal layers and excessive infiltration of mononuclear cells specially lymphocytes and macrophages in case of Bm95 vaccinated animals whereas edematous changes was milder with infiltration of few mononuclear cells in case of BmWE_{Ag} vaccinated animals which might be due to multiplication of lymphocytes and release of macrophage chemotactic factors by lymphokines. The vascular changes were probably mediated through the release of inflammatory mediators and lysosomal enzymes from macrophages (Roitt, 1988), leading to inflammation and swelling of skin at the injection site.

Conclusion

Intradermal immune response was highly positive on day 60 and 40 DPI in Bm95 and BmWE_{Ag} groups of animals respectively as compared to unvaccinated control animals.

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